

Water Quality Index and Correlation Analysis of River Water Parameters: Study on a Section of Turag River near Tongi Industrial Area

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ECR-1997 Standard;
Turag River; Tongi
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ABSTRACT

Research on water quality analysis of physicochemical parameters, different water quality indices, water pollution monitoring etc. of different water bodies was conducted earlier; but recently, water pollution and its effects assessment with WQI model and Statistical tools such as: correlation and regression related research takes significant role for futuristic and detail analysis. This research deals with Water Quality Index and Correlation Analysis on water quality parameter of Turag River adjacent to Tongi industrial area; some selected physicochemical parameters (like as: pH, EC, TDS, TSS, DO, BOD5, and COD) are investigated herein. To know the state of Turag river water quality parameters, water samples were collected from four (04) sites near Tongi industrial area; in order to get the temporal changes, during both wet (October, 2023) and dry (March, 2024) season, 04 water samples were collected accordingly from 04 locations. After samples collection, it was measured, experimented in laboratory and analyzed to ascertain the water quality condition with WQI and correlation matrix through statistical analysis based on tested results of mentioned parameters. The results revealed almost every data of wet season are within standard level of DoE (ECR, 1997). But, During dry season, the values (EC, DO, BOD and COD) near Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd and (TSS, DO, BOD and COD) values near Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd. are not within the acceptable limit respectively; near Tongi Bridge and near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd. the DO values are bellow the acceptable limit according to Inland Surface Water Standard values of DoE (ECR, 1997).The present study shows that, the WQI of o4 stations are within the range of (76-100) in dry season; which indicates water quality is Very Bad and in wet season, all station's data are comparatively low and within the range of (51-75) which is indicating Bad water quality. The finding reported herein the concentration of DO is alarmingly low in the Turag River in dry season. Results also showed that, concentration of EC, TSS, BOD and COD are high dry season. According to WQI scale, in dry season the water quality of Turag river is comparatively very bad than wet season. To minimize the water pollution, it is required to take immediate steps from concern bodies.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Industrial Sectors has very essential role for economic growth and development of a country. There are various industries for example garments and textile industries, chemical factories, pharmaceuticals industries, dyeing and washing industries and paper factories so on. Many Industry and factories are established near running water bodies (such as: rivers, ocean, seas, bays etc.) due to transportation cost is very cheaper than other ways. Those Industries and factories are throwing and dumping their untreated wastewater, wastes, garbage, chemicals, raw materials etc. near bank or into the water bodies, as a result water bodies are polluting day by day in alarming rate. Rahman et al. [1] explained that, In Bangladesh, industrial establishments are built up around river system. "Now-a-days, river's water quality is becoming deteriorated gradually; the useable water sources have been polluted for manmade actions such as over populations, rapid growth of urban centres, increasing of industrialization in fast. There are consequences of pollution on the surrounding land and aquatic ecosystem which ultimately affect the livelihood and community in our country" [1]. Mobin et al. [2] and Meghla et al. [3] explained that, "Dhaka city is surrounded by a number of rivers, wetlands and canals. Four rivers namely Buriganga, Turag, Dhaleshwari and Balu were declared as Ecological Critical Areas by the Department of Environment in September, 2009" [4]. Meghla, Urmly, and Mahamud [5] stated that, among several rivers, the Turag River is particularly affected by sever pollution due to the discharge of untreated industrial waste from various industries. As a result, the physicochemical water parameters of the river water always changing at an alarming rate. According to their findings, "Both organic and inorganic waste effluents that are discharged into the Turag River water adversely interact with the river system and thus deteriorate the water quality of the river" [3]. Moniruzzaman et al. [6] worked titled on "Monitoring Water Quality and Pollution of Shitalakhsa River". In this research they explained that, Different industries besides

the Shitalakhsa River are continuously discharging their effluents and dump into the Shitalakhsa River, so different physiochemical parameters are continuously changing and stands on below standards of water quality [6]. Reza et al. [7] conducted a study titled on "Monitoring Physicochemical Parameters of Turag River Water," in this research they examined about selected physicochemical parameters like: pH, Electrical Conductivity, Total Dissolved Solids, Total Suspended Solids, Dissolved Oxygen, Biological Oxygen Demand, and Chemical Oxygen Demand to investigate the effects of industrial waste on river water. Moniruzzaman et al. [8] analysed that, "Surface Water quality parameters of lake water bodies in the Gulshan and Banani areas of Dhaka and compared them with standard values; their investigation revealed that, the lake water is increasingly polluted due to the continuous discharge of domestic waste, sewage, municipal waste, and other pollutants".

Meghla, Urmly, and Mahamud [5] analysed the seasonal variations in lake water quality in Hatirjheel Lake and Dhanmondi Lake during the period from August, 2019 to January, 2020. The study revealed that, the physicochemical parameters and nutrient status of Dhanmondi Lake water were within the standard limit except EC indicating a rich habitat for aquatic organisms and sounds for recreational activities than Hatirjheel Lake which should be monitored throughout the year to maintain the productivity of lake water systems [5]. According to Bangladesh Centre for Advanced Studies in 2009, only about 40% industries have ETPs. In 10% industries, ETPs are under construction and about 50% industries have no ETP establishment. That is, more than 50% of waste generated by the industries eventually goes to the rivers untreated [4]. During the dry season, the level of the water volume decreases and the condition of the water becomes worse than the wet season [9]. In and around the Dhaka city, approximately 300 outfalls of domestic and industrial effluents developed along with the river bank. The rivers are further polluted by dumping of domestic waste, clinical, pathological wastes and excretory product [10].

Khan et al. [11] studied the water quality index (WQI) of the Turag River and found significant spatial variation. They revealed that, higher WQI found in the northern section of Turag River, with the highest value (84.04) recorded at Rupnagar Pump House. Comparatively, the southern sections exhibited lower water quality, with the lowest WQI value of 40.17 observed at the Palpara Ghat location [11]. Islam et al. [12] conducted study to investigate the surface water quality of the Tista River at Kaunia point during both the wet and dry season. Chowdhury, Ankon, and Bhuiyan [13] assessed the water quality index of the Shitalakshya River near Haripur Power Station and further emphasized on WQI along with seasonal variations during monsoon, pre-monsoon, post-monsoon considering five different years from 2013 to 2018. In this study, they explained about “three different methods to evaluate the WQI named as; Weighted Arithmetic Index Method, Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) WQI Method and National Sanitation Foundation (NSF) Method; Based on WQI values, the Shitalakshya River water was classified as poor water during the aforementioned years” [13]. The WQI is a measure that indicates the combined impact of various water quality parameters [14].

1.2 Problem Statement

Due to Rapid urbanization and industrialization, Tongi Industrial Area is particularly vulnerable area for severe pollution; it receives large volumes of pollutants from textile, dyeing, metal processing, and other manufacturing industries [15], [16]. In this area, most of the industries don't have ETP, although some industries have ETP but these are not in proper operation. Not maintaining the standard water quality of liquid effluent. This contamination threatens aquatic ecosystems [17], [18] and public health [19], [20]. Assessing water quality through the Water Quality Index (WQI) and correlation analysis of key parameters is essential for identifying pollution sources and their interdependencies. This research aims to evaluate water quality and pollutant relationships, providing critical insights for effective pollution control and sustainable water resource management [21].

Despite previous studies on river water pollution in Bangladesh, limited research has specifically focused on the integrated analysis of WQI and parameter correlation in this critical section of the Turag River [2]. The lack of continuous monitoring and data-driven assessments hinders effective policy interventions and water resource management [22]. Without real-time data on water quality, accessibility, usage patterns, and environmental impacts, policymakers and managers are unable to make decisions for sustainable water resource management [23]. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the water quality of the Turag River near the Tongi Industrial Area using WQI and statistical correlation analysis to identify major contaminants with relationships.

1.3 Significance of the Study

Water bodies play a crucial role in sustaining ecosystems, supporting biodiversity, and providing essential water resources for domestic, industrial, and agricultural uses. Moniruzzaman, Pradhan and Huda [21] discuss the Sources, Uses, Significance, challenges and Management of Water bodies in Jashore sadar upazila. Moniruzzaman, Anjum and Huda [24] discussed on spatial distribution and major characteristics of different surface water bodies of Jashore Municipality. They also emphasizes on role of water bodies as its uses, size, shape, association and function as a sources of water resources [24]. Hoque, Saika and Huda conducted a research focusing on small perennial water bodies of Ghiduari Mouza under Atpara Upazila, Netrokona District, they emphasis on spatial distribution, use patterns, and water quality of small water bodies [25]. The Turag River supports aquatic life, biodiversity, and local livelihoods. This research highlights the adverse effects of pollution on the river's ecosystem, guiding conservation efforts and sustainable water resource management. This present research will help to understand the level of pollution in the Turag River near the Tongi Industrial Area, where industrial and municipal waste significantly impact on water quality [7], [26]. By evaluating the WQI and correlation analysing among key water parameters, this study provide a comprehensive assessment of pollution levels and potential

sources. The findings will help for policymakers, environmental agencies, and local authorities to implement effective management of water bodies and watershed along pollution control strategies [27], [28]. The study on the Water Quality Index and Correlation Analysis of River Water Parameters in a Section of the Turag River near Tongi Industrial Area holds importance from environmental, social, and policy-making perspectives. Additionally, the study contributes to the broader field of environmental monitoring by offering valuable data for future research on water bodies pollution and sustainable water resource management [29], [30]. Contaminated river water poses severe health risks to communities relying on it for daily needs. The findings of this present study can be used to assess potential health hazards and promote safe water practices. By providing a comprehensive analysis of water quality trends, this research can support policymakers in developing effective water management strategies, enforcing environmental regulations, and improving wastewater treatment systems. It also helps to determine the river's pollution status and potential health risks and hazards for biotic environments [26]. Understanding seasonal and spatial variations in water quality will aid in designing sustainable strategies for maintaining river health. This study contributes to take long-term efforts for river conservation and pollution mitigation through proper authorities [7].

1.4 Research Aim and Objectives

The research aim is to calculate Water Quality Index and Correlation Analysis with seasonal changes of Turag River Water adjacent to Tongi industrial area. The specific objectives of the research are as follows:

- i. Collecting water samples from research area and mapping of Water Samples Collection Sites;
- ii. To analyze physicochemical parameters of collected water samples and examines water quality during wet season (October, 2023) and dry season (March, 2024);
- iii. To calculate WQI and Statistical Analysis through Correlation Matrix based on experimented data to explore the state of the Turag River water quality with

reference to water quality parameters Standards (ECR-1997) [31].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Selection of Research Area

Research area is Tongi Industrial Area (Gazipur) adjacent to the Turag River in Dhaka City. Turag River is initiated from the Bongshi River, and then it flows along Tongi Industrial Area near Gazipur, Dhaka City. Geographical Location of study area located in between 23°53'26.1"N to 23°54'22.6"N latitudes and 90°23'05.3"E to 90°24'45.6"E longitudes (see Figure 1).

Table 1: Location of Sample Collection Sites.

SL. No.	Sample Sites Name	Geographical Location
S1	Near Tongi Bridge	Latitude: 23°53'30.90"N
		Longitude: 90°23'23.60"E
S2	Near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd.	Latitude: 23°53'37.93"N
		Longitude: 90°23'21.20"E
S3	Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.	Latitude: 23°53'40.82"N
		Longitude: 90°23'19.31"E
S4	Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.	Latitude: 23°53'55.99"N
		Longitude: 90°23'9.75"E

Source: GPS Survey by Author, 2023-2024

2.2 Sources of Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data were collected to achieve the research aim and objectives. All the necessary data were collected from different sources and methods. Primary data sources were refer to direct field sites which were conducted into such ways: Collection of water samples, taking GPS reading of sample sites and taking photographs. Secondary data were collected from different sources and methods according to research needs. In order to literature review and conceptualization, data and information will be collected from different published and

unpublished journals, reports, research papers of different government and nongovernment organizations etc.

Figure 1. Map of Research area showing Location of Water Samples Collection Sites.

Source: Compiled by Author, 2024

Figure 2. Methodological Flow Chart of the Research

2.3 Samples Preparation Process, Material Used and Laboratory Procedure

Four (04) water samples were collected from the field area. In this research, the water samples were collected at October 2023 and March 2024, which correspond to the wet season and dry season respectively. After collecting data, it was experimented in the laboratory. Experimented data, were collected as water samples from different sites and analysed to ascertain the water quality of specific physicochemical parameters such as: pH, EC, TDS, TSS, DO, BOD5, and COD were measured and analysed in the laboratory. For analysis of water parameter, different instruments were used. Such as: pH measured by Digital pH meter (Model: HI2210, HANNA); EC and TDS were gauged by using a Multi meter (Model: HQ40d, HACH Instrument); TSS and DO were measured by using a Portable Spectrophotometer (Model: DR1900, HACH Instrument); BOD was tested by BOD incubator and BOD tank; and COD was estimated by using the Reactor Digestion Method.

2.4 Water Quality Index (WQI)

Water quality index was calculated using Weighted Arithmetic Water Quality Index (WAWQI) method. Various scientists have utilized this method extensively such as: Balan, Shivakumar and Kumar [32] and the following equation were used to calculate the WQI by Brown et al. [33]:

Equation for Water Quality Index Calculation:

$$WAWQI = \frac{\sum Qiwi}{\sum wi}$$

Where,

$$Wi \text{ (Unit Weight)} = \frac{K}{Sn};$$

Here 'K' is calculated by formula:

$$K = \left\{ 1 / \left(\sum \frac{1}{Sn} \right) \right\}$$

$$Qi \text{ (Quality rating)} = \left[\frac{(Vn - Vi)}{(Sn - Vi)} \right] \times 100$$

Here, **Vn** represent estimated value; **Vi** represent ideal value (0 for all parameters except pH and DO which are 7.0 and 14.6 mg/ L respectively) and **Sn** represent standard permissible value of parameters [31].

2.5 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is very useful statistical measures to examine the relationship among different water quality parameters by Karl Pearson Correlation co-efficient formula [34]:

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Where, r= correlation co-efficient; x_i = values of the 'x' variable; \bar{x} = mean of the values of the 'x' variable; y_i = values of the 'y' variable; and \bar{y} = mean of the values of the 'y' variable. When, r= (+1), then co-efficient of correlation is called the Perfect Positive Correlation; r= (-1), then co-efficient of correlation is called the Perfect Negative Correlation; r= (0), then it indicates there is no correlation among the variables; if $-1 < r < 0$ then it indicated partial Negative Correlation and $0 < r < 1$ then it indicated partial Positive Correlation.

2.6 Techniques of Data Analysis

The collected data were summarized, tabulated and analysed by using the Microsoft Office and Microsoft Excel software. Research area map was created using Esri's ArcGIS 10.8 Desktop GIS software. Statistical Tools or formula such as: mean, standard deviation, variance, correlation etc were calculated by SPSS software.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Water Quality Parameters

Water pH: Figure 3 represents the pH during both wet and dry seasons. The pH value of sample 01 (Near Tongi Bridge) was 7.48 and 7.07; sample 02 (Near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd.) was 7.73 and 7.14; sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) was 7.48 and 7.03, and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) was 7.47 and 7.02, as are shown in Table 1. The pH value varied from 7.02 to 7.73. According to ECR-1997, standard pH value

range is 6.5 to 8.5. So pH levels are within acceptable limits in this area, but the pH values of 04 samples are higher in the wet season than in the dry season.

Figure 3. Representation of Water pH values.

Electrical Conductivity (EC): EC values during both wet and dry seasons are present in Figure 4. During both the wet and dry seasons, the EC value of sample 01 (Near Tongi Bridge) was 680 and 746; sample 02 (Near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd.) was 690 and 754; sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) was 705 and 777; and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) was 655 and 1205 accordingly. These values varied from 655 to 1205. The average EC values of 04 samples during both wet and dry seasons are 682.5 and 872, respectively. Here, it is clear that the average EC values of 04 samples are higher in the dry season than in the wet season. Except for the value of sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) during the dry season, the rests of the EC values are within the acceptable limit according to the ECR-1997 standard value of electrical conductivity of 1200 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

Figure 4. Graphical Representation of EC.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS): In Figure 5, the TDS value of the wet and dry seasons is presented. The TDS value of sample 01 (Near

Tongi Bridge) was 270 and 395; sample 02 (Near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd.) was 255 and 368; sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) was 290 and 408; and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) was 229 and 642 during both the wet and dry seasons. The average TDS values of 04 samples during both wet and dry seasons are 261 and 460.75, respectively. The average TDS values of 04 samples are higher in the dry season than in the wet season. The TDS value varied from 229 to 642, which are within the acceptable limit; according to the ECR-1997 standard, the value of TDS is 2100 mg/L.

Figure 5. Graphical Representation of TDS.

Total Suspended Solids (TSS): Figure 6 showed the TSS concentrations during both wet and dry seasons graphically. TSS value of sample 01 (Near Tongi Bridge) was 21 and 106; sample 02 (Near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd.) was 17 and 58; sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) was 22 and 153; and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) was 24 and 148. These values varied from 17 to 153. The average TSS values of 04 samples are higher in the dry season than in the wet season. Except for the value of sample 03 during dry seasons, the rests of TSS values are within the acceptable limit according to the ECR-1997 standard level (TSS 150 mg/L).

Figure 6. Representation of TSS values.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO): Figure 7 represents the DO level during both wet and dry seasons. The DO value of sample 01 (Near Tongi Bridge) was 6.5 and 2.1; sample 02 (Near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd.) was 6.5 and 2.2; sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) was 6.6 and 2.2; and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) was 6.4 and 2.4. These values varied from 2.1 to 6.6. During the dry season, all DO values are below the acceptable limit, but during the wet season, all values are within the acceptable limit according to the ECR-1997, (the standard value of DO is 6 mg/L). The average DO values of 04 samples during both wet and dry seasons are 6.5 and 2.2, respectively. So, the average DO values of 04 samples are lower in the dry season than in the wet seasons.

Figure 7. Representation of DO values.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD): Figure 8 is the graphical representation of BOD values during both wet and dry seasons. BOD value of sample 01 (Near Tongi Bridge) were 20 and 43; sample 02 (Near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd.) were 22 and 31; sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) were 22 and 224; and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) were 33 and 255. These values varied from 22 to 255. Except for the value of sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) during the dry season.

Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) were 21 and 131; and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) were 28 and 160. Accordingly, these values varied from 20 to 160. Except for the value of sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) during the dry season, the rests of the BOD values are within the acceptable limit according to the ECR-1997 standard level of BOD (50 mg/L). The average BOD values of 04 samples during both wet and dry seasons are 22.75 and 91.25, accordingly.

Figure 8. Graphical Representation of BOD values during wet and dry seasons.

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD): Figure 9 explains the COD values during both wet and dry seasons. COD value of sample 01 (Near Tongi Bridge) were 42 and 197; sample 02 (Near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd) were 46 and 86; sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) were 32 and 224; and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) were 33 and 255. These values varied from 32 to 255. Except for the value of sample 03 (Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd.) and sample 04 (Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd.) during the dry season. The average COD values of 04 samples during both wet and dry seasons are 38 and 190.5, respectively.

Figure 9. Graphical Representation of COD values during wet and dry seasons.

Table 1. The Measured Values of the Water Quality Parameters with Standards.

S/N	Parameter (Unit)	Season	Measured Values				Statistical Value		DoE Standard (ECR, 1997)
			WS ₁	WS ₂	WS ₃	WS ₄	Mean(\bar{x})	SD (σ)	
1	pH	Wet	7.48	7.73	7.48	7.47	7.54	0.13	6.5-8.5
		Dry	7.07	7.14	7.03	7.02	7.08	0.05	
2	EC ($\mu\text{s/cm}$)	Wet	680	690	705	655	682.5	21.02	1200 ($\mu\text{s/cm}$)
		Dry	746	754	777	1205*	872	223.93	
3	TDS (mg/l)	Wet	270	255	290	229	261	25.70	2100 mg/l
		Dry	395	368	408	642	460.75	126.93	
4	TSS (mg/l)	Wet	21	17	22	24	21	2.94	150 mg/l
		Dry	106	58	153*	148	116.25	44.18	
5	DO (mg/l)	Wet	6.5	6.5	6.6	6.4	6.5	0.08	6 mg/l
		Dry	2.1*	2.2*	2.2*	2.4*	2.2	0.13	
6	BOD (mg/l)	Wet	20	22	21	28	58	3.59	50 mg/l
		Dry	43	31	131*	160*	91.25	63.94	
7	COD (mg/l)	Wet	42	46	32	33	38	6.85	200 mg/l
		Dry	197	86	224*	255*	190.5	73.59	

WS₁= Water Sample 1, WS₂= Water Sample 2, WS₃= Water Sample 3, WS₄= Water Sample 4, SD= Standard Deviation, Dry Season (March, 2024) and Wet Season (October, 2023). (*) sign indicate the Values are not within the Standard level.

3.2 Water Quality Index (WQI)

Table 2. Calculated Values of Water Quality Index (WQI) for Dry Season.

SL/N	Parameter (Unit)	Water Quality Rating (Qi)				Unit Weight (Wi)	Water Quality Index (QiWi)			
		S1	S2	S3	S4		S1	S2	S3	S4
1	pH	4.7	9.3	2	1.3	0.3708	1.7	3.46	0.74	0.49
2	EC ($\mu\text{s/cm}$)	62.2	62.8	64.75	100.4	0.0026	0.2	0.17	0.17	0.26
3	TDS (mg/l)	18.8	17.5	19.429	30.6	0.0015	0.0	0.03	0.03	0.05
4	TSS (mg/l)	70.7	38.7	102	98.7	0.0210	1.5	0.81	2.14	2.07
5	DO (mg/l)	145.3	144.2	144.186	141.9	0.5253	76.3	75.74	75.74	74.52
6	BOD(mg/l)	86.0	62.0	262	320.0	0.0630	5.4	3.91	16.52	20.17
7	COD(mg/l)	98.5	43.0	112	127.5	0.0158	1.6	0.68	1.77	2.01
$\Sigma w_i=1.00$							86.7	84.79	97.10	99.57

Table 3. Calculated Values of Water Quality Index (WQI) for Wet Season.

SL/N	Parameter (Unit)	Water Quality Rating (Qi)				Unit Weight (Wi)	Water Quality Index (QiWi)			
		S1	S2	S3	S4		S1	S2	S3	S4
1	pH	32.0	48.67	32.0	31.33	0.3708	11.87	18.05	11.87	11.62
2	EC ($\mu\text{s/cm}$)	56.7	57.50	58.8	54.58	0.0026	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.14

3	TDS (mg/l)	12.9	12.14	13.8	10.91	0.0015	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
4	TSS (mg/l)	14.0	11.33	14.7	16.00	0.0210	0.29	0.24	0.31	0.34
5	DO (mg/l)	94.2	94.19	93.0	95.35	0.5253	49.47	49.47	48.86	50.09
6	BOD(mg/l)	40.0	44.00	42.0	56.00	0.0630	2.52	2.77	2.65	3.53
7	COD(mg/l)	21.0	23.00	16.0	16.50	0.0158	0.33	0.36	0.25	0.26
						Σwi=1.00	64.65	71.06	64.11	65.99

Table 1 (titled as “The Measured Values of the Water Quality Parameters with Standards”) represented obtained data from laboratory tests on selected physicochemical parameters of water quality of the Turag River. Almost every data point of the wet season is within the standard level of DoE [31]. But, during the dry season, the values of EC, DO, BOD, and COD near

Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd. and the values of TSS, DO, BOD, and COD near Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd. are not within the acceptable limit, respectively; near Tongi Bridge and near Sajid Washing & Dyeing Ltd., the DO values are below the acceptable limit according to Inland Surface Water Standard values of DoE

3.3 Statistical Analysis by Correlation Matrix

Table 4. Correlation matrix of water quality parameters of Turag River.

SL No.	Water Quality Parameters	pH	EC (µs/cm)	TDS (mg/l)	TSS (mg/l)	DO (mg/l)	BOD (mg/l)	COD (mg/l)
1	pH	1						
2	EC (µs/cm)	-0.59	1					
3	TDS (mg/l)	-0.79	0.95**	1				
4	TSS (mg/l)	-0.89	0.70	0.85*	1			
5	DO (mg/l)	0.94**	-0.53	-0.75	-0.86*	1		
6	BOD (mg/l)	-0.71	0.83	0.87*	0.91**	-0.64	1	
7	COD (mg/l)	-0.87	0.74	0.88*	0.99**	-0.85*	0.88*	1

(**) Indicates at 1% significant level; (*) Indicates at 5% significant level.

The study showed that the parameters are linearly correlated to a large extent. Table 4 is showing the correlation matrix of the water sample, which shows a partial positive correlation ($0 < r < 1$) between pH and DO ($r=0.94$); EC and TDS ($r=0.95$); EC and TSS ($r=0.70$); EC and BOD ($r=0.83$); EC and COD ($r=0.74$); TDS and TSS ($r=0.85$); TDS and BOD ($r=0.87$); TDS and COD ($r=0.88$); TSS and BOD

[31]. The WQI ranges have been defined as follows: 0-25 indicates excellent water quality; 26-50 indicates good water quality; 51-75 indicates bad water quality; 76-100 indicates very bad water quality; and 100 and above indicates unsuitable for drinking [33], [35], [36]. In research, Table 2 (titled as “Calculated Values of Water Quality Index (WQI) for Dry Season”) and Table 3 (titled as “Calculated Values of Water Quality Index (WQI) for Wet Season”) represented the Water Quality Index based on the WAWQI formula, where, it is clearly shown that, in the dry seasons the WQI of Four stations are within the range of 76-100, which indicates water quality is very bad. And in the wet season, all stations data are within the range of 51-75, which is indicates bad water quality.

($r=0.91$); TSS and COD ($r=0.99$); BOD and COD ($r=0.88$). Similarly, some partial negative correlations ($-1 < r < 0$) are shown between pH and EC ($r= -0.59$); pH and TDS ($r= -0.79$); pH and TSS ($r= -0.89$); pH and BOD ($r= -0.71$); pH and COD ($r= -0.87$); EC and DO ($r= -0.53$); TDS and DO ($r= -0.75$); TSS and DO ($r= -0.86$); DO and BOD ($r= -0.64$); DO and COD ($r= -0.85$).

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, it is clear that the Turag River was excessively polluted by the discharge of industrial effluents, sewage waste, agricultural and city runoff, and anthropogenic activities [37]. During the dry season, the values (EC, DO,

BOD, and COD) near Ultra Washing and Dyeing Ltd. and the values (TSS, DO, BOD and COD) near Zarina Composite Textile Industries Ltd. are not within the acceptable limits, respectively; near Tongi Bridge and near Sajid Washing & Dyeing

Ltd., the DO values are below the acceptable limits. Water quality parameters of the Turag River are not within standard values during the dry season compared to the wet season. During the dry season, the WQI of four stations is within the range of 76-100, which indicates very bad water quality. And in the wet season, all stations data are within the range of 51-75, which indicates bad water quality. There are some recommendations to protect the water bodies and improve water quality, Such as Implementations of law and regulations about water quality, water bodies [24] and watershed protection, preservation and management [38]; Monitoring and properly maintaining the Urban

Solid waste Management [39], Effluent Treatment Plant for each industry; Preventing such activities, diminish the water bodies/natural habitats of fish [40], deteriorating water quality; Have to take the proper measures to reduce the use of agrochemicals and pesticides [26]; Increasing public awareness and social development program by seminars, symposiums, posturing, exhibitions and mass media [2]. Now is the right time to be aware and take proper steps to protect the existing water bodies and their water quality [3] so that we can protect our environment to lead a healthy, wealthy, and happy life in the future.

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